

Detailed description of the **source data file** for the article “Unsupervised experience with temporal continuity of the visual environment is causally involved in the development of V1 complex cells” by Giulio Matteucci and Davide Zoccolan.

The source data file contains two cell arrays and a matrix in Matlab format (.mat).

To explain the structure of these arrays, let's define the following variables:

G represents the animal group from which the recordings were carried out:

- $G = 1$ (control group)
- $G = 2$ (experimental group)

N is an index referring to the neurons recorded in V1 of animals from each group. As reported in the article, we have that:

- *N* ranges from 1 to 105 for control group
- *N* ranges from 1 to 158 for experimental group

As described in the Materials and Methods section of the paper, during recordings the animals were exposed to moving gratings of different direction, spatial and temporal frequencies as well to a spatiotemporally-correlated noise movies.

SF is an index identifying the spatial frequency of a grating stimulus.

- $SF = 1$ (0.02 cyc/°)
- $SF = 2$ (0.04 cyc/°)

TF is an index identifying the temporal frequency of a grating stimulus.

- $TF = 1$ (2 Hz)
- $TF = 2$ (4 Hz)

DIR is an index identifying the drift direction of a grating stimulus.

- *DIR* ranges from 0° to 330° in steps of 10°

TRIAL is an index identifying the presentation trial number of a specific grating stimulus.

- *TRIAL* ranges from 1 to 20

NOISE is an index referring to the spatiotemporally-correlated noise movie chunks.

- *NOISE* ranges from 1 to 40

FRAME is an index referring to the frames of each noise movie chunk.

- *FRAME* ranges from 1 to 1818

st_array_grating: nested cell array containing the spike times for each spike produced during each individual presentation of each grating stimulus for each neuron in the two groups. The outer cell array has dimension $1 \times G_{\max}$. The inner cell arrays (referring to control animals for $G=1$ and to experimental animals for $G=2$) have dimension $N_{\max} \times SF_{\max} \times TF_{\max} \times DIR_{\max} \times TRIAL_{\max}$. Each cell contains a vector storing spike timestamps. Note that all spike times contained in this cell array are in seconds and referred to the stimulus onset time. As described in the Materials and Methods section of the paper, each grating stimulus remained on screen, drifting up to 1.5 s after stimulus onset time (presented at 60 Hz refresh rate).

grating_params: data structure with fields SFs, TFs, DIRS and TRIALS containing vectors listing the possible values of these grating stimuli parameters in the same order in which response spike times are organized withing **st_array_grating** (the same also described above).

st_array_noise: nested cell array containing the spike times of spikes produced by each individual presentation of each noise stimulus for each neuron in the two groups. The outer cell array has dimension $1 \times G_{\max}$. The inner cell arrays (referring to control animals for $G=1$ and to experimental animals for $G=2$) have dimension $N_{\max} \times NOISE_{\max} \times FRAME_{\max}$. Each cell contains a vector storing spike timestamps. Note that all spike times contained in this cell array are in seconds and referred to the noise stimulus onset time (and organized by noise movie frames). As described in the Materials and Methods section of the paper, each spatiotemporally-correlated noise movie had a duration of 60 s (presented at 30 Hz refresh rate).

corr_noise_frames: matrix containing all frames of each spatiotemporally-correlated noise movie. These data are necessary for carrying out STA analysis on noise movie spiking responses contained in **st_array_noise**. As described in the Materials and Methods section of the paper noise movies contained in this data structure were presented in higher resolution to the animal. Stored in this matrix you can find a highly downsampled version of the same movies (the one that has been used for carrying out STA analysis described in the paper). For details on how the movies were generated see Materials and Methods section of the paper. The matrix has dimensions $PIXH \times PIXW \times NOISE_{\max} \times FRAME_{\max}$. Where $PIXH=18$ and $PIXW=32$ are the height and width in pixels, respectively, of each movie frame.